

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH TERVALENT METALS. PART III. CHROMIUM PHENYLBIGUANIDINES.

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Preparation, properties and the composition of the chromium *tris*-phenylbiguanide base and its salts have been described in the present paper. The constitution of the complex has also been discussed.

In Part I of this series the preparation, properties and constitution of the chromium *tris*-biguanide base and its salts have been described (Rây and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 15, 670). In the present paper we have studied the properties of the complexes formed by a substituted biguanide, phenylbiguanide (I) with the same metal. The free chromium *tris*-phenylbiguanide base has been prepared and converted into a number of its salts. The properties of these substances differ somewhat from those of the corresponding simple biguanide complexes. The fact that the chromium *tris*-phenylbiguanide forms a stable hydroxide, carbonate and a number of salts which dissociate in aqueous solution like the corresponding ammonium salt, without appreciable hydrolysis, indicates that the co-ordination with the metal atom occurs at (1) and co-valence at (4), as shown in (II). The alternative possibility with co-valence at (2) and co-ordination at (5) would leave only C_6H_5NH -group free to form salts in combination with acids. But such salts would dissociate like aniline salts in solution differing widely from those described in this paper. The basic character of the chromium *tris*-phenylbiguanide complex is, therefore, due to the free amino-group at (5). This, as well as the formation of the anhydrous base—chromium *tris*-phenylbiguanide—furnish additional evidences in support of the constitution of chromium biguanidines or, for the matter of that, of the metal-biguanide complexes in general, as deduced in Part I (Ray and Saha, *loc. cit.*).

(I)

(II)

An interesting fact was observed regarding the properties of the hydrated base. The crude base, which is soluble in alcohol, on recrystallisation from the alcoholic solution becomes insoluble in the same solvent. This seems to suggest a slow polymerisation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenylbiguanide hydrochloride was prepared from aniline hydrochloride and dicyandiamide by heating them in alcoholic solution with a reflux

condenser on a water-bath for about two hours (Smolka and Friedrich, *Monatsh.*, 1888, 9, 227).

Chromium tris-Phenylbiguanide Hydroxide.—Phenylbiguanide hydrochloride (15 g.) was treated with a solution of chromium chloride and a moderately strong solution of caustic soda in excess. The mixture was then heated on the water-bath when a deep red oil commenced to separate; the heating was continued for about half an hour after this. The supernatant alkaline liquid was then poured off and the oily layer was washed several times with ice-cold water in which it was insoluble. The oil gradually solidified to a crystalline mass. It was then extracted with alcohol; the alcoholic filtrate was mixed with a little water and allowed to stand overnight, when the crystals of the base separated in a pure state. The product, thus obtained, did not, however, redissolve in alcohol. The crystals were washed with alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 and KOH.

The substance forms rose-red crystals, almost insoluble in water. It reacts alkaline to litmus and liberates ammonia when heated with ammonium salt solutions; m.p. 196° with decomposition. {Found: N, 33.30; Cr, 8.19; H_2O , 8.67. [X] (OH) $_3$ requires N, 33.12; Cr, 8.20; H_2O , 8.52 per cent}. where X=Cr (PhBigH $^+$) $_3$ and PhBigH=one phenylbiguanide molecule.

The substance lost two molecules of water at 110° and became anhydrous at 135° .

Chromium tris-Phenylbiguanide Hydrochloride.—The hydrochloride was prepared by just dissolving the preceding base in cold dilute hydrochloric acid avoiding an excess of the latter. The clear solution was cooled in ice; when rose-red crystals of the hydrochloride separated from the latter. These were washed with a little ice-cold water and dried in vacuum over concentrated H_2SO_4 . The hydrochloride is soluble in water, but more readily in alcohol and acetone. {Found: N, 30.61; Cl, 15.20; Cr, 7.37. [X]Cl $_3$ requires N, 30.45; Cl, 15.44; Cr, 7.53 per cent}.

Equivalent conductivity at 0°.

V ... 32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048
Λ ... 47.14	52.81	54.12	57.28	59.19	61.45	63.04

Equivalent conductivity of ammonium chloride at 0° amounts to 81.3 mhos at 1024 v and that of $1/3 \text{ La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ at infinite dilution at the same temperature is about 67-69 mhos. Hence the result is in good agreement with the adopted constitution for the complex.

Mol. Wt. from the freezing-point.

Substance per 100 g. water	Depression Δ .	Mol. wt. m .	Vant Hoff's factor $i = M/m$.	Degree of dissociation $\alpha = (i-1)/n-1$.
1.015	0.097°	194.8	3.54	0.847
0.508	0.049	194.9	3.57	0.857

From conductivity at corresponding dilutions at 0°, α is approximately 0.81.

Chromium tris-phenylbiguanide hydrobromide was prepared from the hydrochloride in cold concentrated solution by the addition of a concentrated solution of KBr. The pale rose crystals were washed and dried as in the previous case. Properties resemble those of the chloride. {Found: Br, 28.94; Cr, 6.41. [X] Br₃ requires Br, 29.16; Cr, 6.31 per cent}.

Chromium tris-phenylbiguanide hydriodide was prepared as in the case of hydrobromide from a cold strong solution of the hydrochloride by the addition of concentrated KI solution. The pale rose-coloured crystals were washed and dried as before. It resembles the other halides in properties. [Found: I, 39.22; Cr, 5.27. [X] I₃ requires I, 39.52; Cr, 5.39 per cent].

Chromium tris-phenylbiguanide nitrate was obtained as rose-red crystals from a cold strong solution of the hydrochloride and potassium nitrate. The substance is soluble in water, alcohol and acetone. {Found: Cr, 6.82; NO₃, 23.80. [X](NO₃)₃ requires Cr, 6.76; NO₃, 24.18 per cent}.

Chromium tris-phenylbiguanide chromate was prepared like the previous salts from a cold strong solution of the hydrochloride and a concentrated solution of potassium chromate. It separates as biscuit coloured crystals, very sparingly soluble in water and insoluble in alcohol. {Found: Cr(total), 16.80; Cr(as CrO₄), 10.24. [X]₂(CrO₄)₃ requires Cr(total), 17.17. Cr(as CrO₄), 10.30 per cent}.

Chromium tris-Phenylbiguanide Sulphate.—On treating a solution of the hydrochloride with a solution of ammonium sulphate, the crystalline precipitate, which separated, always contained some chlorine. The pure sulphate was, however, obtained by digesting in the cold the chromium *tris-phenylbiguanide* base with a slight excess of N/10-H₂SO₄ for about 24 hours. The product was washed and dried as usual. It forms pale rose crystals, very sparingly soluble in water. {Found: S, 6.32; Cr, 6.93. [X]₂(SO₄)₃, 2H₂O requires S, 6.44; Cr, 7.0 per cent}.

A solution of the chloride was found to give the following precipitate with solutions of

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|------------------------------------|-----|-----|-------------------|
| 1. Sodium thiosulphate | ... | ... | pale rose-red |
| 2. Sodium bicarbonate or carbonate | ... | ... | lavender coloured |
| 3. Sodium nitrate | ... | ... | biscuit-coloured |
| 4. Potassium cobalticyanide | ... | ... | pale pink |
| 5. Potassium ferrocyanide | ... | ... | biscuit-coloured |
| 6. Potassium ferricyanide | ... | ... | yellow |